

**Upgrade
data steward**

You draw 1 card
when you play a
shared project

**Upgrade
exploited PhD
student**

You can play an
additional card in
your turn

**Upgrade
Dataverse**

When others publish
on a shared project
of yours, they and
you can draw a card

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